

Adequate Funding of National Universities Commission for Effective Universities Supervision in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the importance of providing adequate funding for the National Universities Commission for effective university supervision in Nigeria. Qualitative and quantitative data were used in the paper. The data were collected from online publication and print materials. The paper depends on primary and secondary data. The paper identified inadequate funding, shortage of personnel, opposition from labour unions, inadequate supervision materials and ineffective capacity building as the challenges facing National Universities Commission in Nigeria. The paper also concluded that adequate funding of the National Universities Commission will lead to; infrastructural development, employment of adequate staff, effective capacity building, expansion of zonal offices, effective programme accreditation, improvement in quality of supervision and improvement in the quality of National Universities Commission services. The paper hereby recommended that the government should ensure adequate funding for the National universities commission.

Keywords: Funding, National Universities Commission, Universities.

Introduction

Adequate funding is critical for the development of any public institution. Adequate funding is the key to the achievement of the institution's goals. Adequate funding is the life wire of any organization. No meaningful impact institutions can attain without adequate funding. Studies have shown that public institutions exceed their mandate when they are adequately funded by the government (Ayuba, 2015). It has been observed that public institutions in Nigeria are underfunded and this has affected the performance of the institutions. Boards, agencies and commissions like the National universities commission are not exempted from the problem of poor funding. Poor budgetary allocation to a public institution like the National universities commission has impacted negatively the discharge of their constitutional functions. The poor funding of public establishments has limited their expansion in terms of service delivery. For instance, The **Executive Secretary of the National Universities Commission observed that in the** fiscal year of 2019, NUC's budget receipt from its capital and overhead allocations had been quite low, with the performance based on the releases put at 50 percent for Overhead Costs and the Personnel Costs at 72 percent up-to-date

since the salaries payment comes through the Integrated Personnel Payroll Information System (IPPIS). (NUC, 2019). It is against this background that this paper discusses the importance of adequate funding of the National Universities Commission for effective university supervision in Nigeria.

Purpose of this Paper

The purpose of this paper is to discuss the importance of providing adequate funding for the National Universities Commission for effective university supervision in Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. to look at the function of the National University Commission;
2. to identify challenges militating against the effectiveness of the National University Commission;
3. To discuss the concept of university supervision; and
4. To discuss the importance of providing adequate funding for the National University Commission for effective university supervision.

Methodology

In this paper, we discussed the importance of providing adequate funding for the National Universities Commission for effective supervision of Nigerian universities for sustainable development. We adopted the content analysis method for the paper. This paper depends on primary and secondary data which were collected from online and print pieces of literature. The data were collected from critical review of published articles from reputable international journals such as CEON, Elsevier, Hindawi, JSTOR, IEEE, Learn Techlib SAGE, Nebraska and Springer.

Conceptual Framework

Concept of National Universities Commission

National Universities Commission is a public institution established to supervise the universities in Nigeria. National Universities Commission is one of the commissions enacted by law to oversee the external administration of the universities. National Universities Commission is an institution of the government with the mandate to manage the universities in the country. The National Universities Commission is a quality assurance institution meant to foster quality in the Nigerian university system. National universities commission coordinates the development of universities in Nigeria. Allocate and disburse federal grants and external aids to universities. Research and advice executive on topics relating to higher education development in Nigeria.

Functions of the National Universities Commission

The National Universities Commission was established in 1962 as an advisory agency in the Cabinet Office. However, in 1974, it became a statutory body and the first Executive Secretary, in the person of Prof. Jibril Aminu was then appointed. The National Universities Commission (NUC) is a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Education (FME). The Commission has a Governing Council, its **Executive Secretary is Prof. Abubakar Adamu Rasheed mni, MFR**, who assumed office **on August 3, 2016 (NUC, 2022)**.

The Commission has twelve Directorates; the Directorate of Academic Planning, Directorate of Inspection and Monitoring, Directorate of Management Support Services, Directorate of the Establishment of Private Universities, Directorate of Students Support Services, Directorate of Research, Innovations & Information Technology, Directorate of Finance and Accounts, Directorate of Accreditation, Directorate of Open and Distance Education, Directorate of Liaison Services and International Cooperation, Directorate of Corporate Communications, and the Directorate of the Executive Secretary's Office. Each of the Directorates is headed by a Director.

The Commission has recorded several successes since its inception. These successes can be attributed to the quality of leadership, dedication and commitment of the staff, the quality of its Board members, cooperation received from Universities and support from the Federal Government.

As a coordinating body, the Commission ensures it discharges its responsibilities by recruiting adequate and relevant manpower and appealing to the Universities for their sustained support and understanding. The Commission also relies on support from the Federal Government, State Governments and other stakeholders in its bid to improve the quality of tertiary education and graduates of the nation's university system, (NUC, 2022).

The main functions of the Commission are outlined as follows:

- i. Approving all academic programmes offered in Nigerian universities;
- ii. Approving the establishment of all higher educational institutions offering degree programmes in Nigerian universities;
- iii. Ensure quality assurance of all academic programmes offered in Nigerian universities;
- iv. Channel for all external support to the Nigerian universities (NUC, 2022).

Ogunode & Adana (2022); NEEDS (2014) and Ehichoya & Ogunode (2020) submitted that the National Universities Commission was established in 1962 and the functions of the NUC include: to coordinate the entire activities in all Nigeria universities; to harmonize and co-ordinate the development of Nigeria universities to meet the national goals; to advise the government on the financial needs of the universities; to distribute funds to the Universities when such is made available by the government; to set the minimum benchmark for Nigerian universities; to ensure compliance of the Universities to the minimum bench mark standard; to Collect, collate, analyze and store data collected from Nigerian Universities for use in advising the government on the need to expand the existing universities or establish new ones; to set standards to be followed in establishing universities in Nigeria; to issue operating license to Nigerian universities; to accredits courses in Nigerian universities; to participate in universities annual estimate hearings to determine the financial need of the universities; and to Keep accurate and up-to-date financial records for all local and foreign transactions (Ogunode & Samuel 2022).

Figure1: Conceptual Framework of NUC Functions
Source: Ogunode & Ayoko (2023)

Concept of University Supervision

Supervision is an organized programme meant to give direction, guidance and control to an individual, organization or institution to improve their performance and ensure they are doing the right things. Supervision is carried out in all forms of educational institutions including higher institutions. Higher institutions supervision is more advanced and complex because the institutions are advanced institutions that deal with teaching, researching and provision of community services (Ogunode & Adana 2022).

University supervision is the act or process of providing advice, guidance and direction to institutions to help the institutions to achieve their objectives. Higher institutions supervision is the *monitoring* of people, activities, programmes offered in the institutions by providing the institutions with professional advice geared towards improving their performance. Higher institutions supervision is an organized activity or programme that is designed to improve the institutions by checking both human and material resources of the institutions through the provision of professional guidance, advice and correction that would help the institution to improve and achieve its goals (Ogunode & Adana 2022).

Challenges Faced by National Universities Commission

There are many challenges National Universities Commission is facing. For this paper, the following; inadequate funding, shortage of personnel, opposition from labour unions, inadequate supervision materials, ineffective capacity building and poor release of the budget would be discussed as part of the challenges facing National Universities Commission in Nigeria.

Inadequate Funding

Inadequate funding of various regulating commissions such as the National Universities Commission [NUC], the National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE] and the National Board for Technical Education [NBTE] is responsible for weak supervision of institutions in Nigeria. The various regulating commissions derive their annual budgetary allocation from the general federal education budget which has been described as inadequate (Ogunode 2020; Ogunode & Babatunde, 2021). Adewale (2017), in Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) identified the shortage of funds as the bane to the development of public commissions and agencies established by the federal government to provide key functions in the country. He went further and said "Many commissions established in Nigeria are under-performing because of the challenges of funding. Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) noted that the funds allocated by the federal government for the administration of university education in Nigeria are not adequate to effectively implement all the universities' programmes such as supervision. The federal government have not provided adequate funding for these institutions to enable them to discharge their mandate as stipulated in the act establishing the respective commissions and agencies. Supervision of instruction at the university level by the school administrators and other management teams like the Directors, Deans and heads of departments is also hampered by poor funding of the universities.

Shortage of Personnel

Shortage of staff in the various commissions is another problem hindering the effective supervision of higher institutions in Nigeria. Staff are employed to help in the implementation of the organizational mandate. The number of staff organizations has helped to some extent in determining how fast they are carrying out their mandate. Personnel are key resources an organization needed most to actualize its goals in the organization. Majorities of supervisory commissions in Nigeria are faced with the problem of inadequate personnel which is hindering their performance. Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) cited Adewale (2017) who did a study that examined the problems facing the public commissions and agencies in Nigeria and discovered that many commissions and agencies of the Federal Government are understaffed and the problem is affecting the implementation of their statutory functions. Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) submitted that the shortage of professional supervisors (personnel) is a big problem preventing effective supervision of universities in Nigeria.

The National Universities Commission was set up by the Nigerian government to handle the supervision of universities in Nigeria. The Executive Secretary of the National Universities Commission (NUC), Professor Abubakar Adamu Rasheed, submitted that "the Commission's staff numerical strength as at 2018, was 688 and that it dropped to 642 in 2019 and 628 by the year 2020 due to retirement of some staff and movement by others". The Punch Editorial Board's comment of August 16, 2013, noted that regulating more than 129 universities in Nigeria effectively is increasingly becoming, a burden too heavy for the National Universities Commission to bear alone. This is because, the staff capacity of the commission, is still small to handle the supervision of all the universities in the country. Presently, the numbers of universities in Nigeria is over 200.

Opposition from Labor Unions

Opposition from some labour unions in higher institutions especially the universities is also a challenge to the supervision of the various supervisory commissions. Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) submitted that opposition from the academic staff union of Nigerian universities is another problem preventing the National Universities Commission from effectively supervising the universities in Nigeria. The Academic Staff Union of Universities is claiming that the universities are enjoying autonomy and so, the universities do not need an external regulatory commission. Olaleye & Oyewole, (2016) and Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) noted that the NUC has been accused of usurping the role of the Senate on the issue of accreditation which hitherto was the responsibility of individual Universities.

Inadequate Supervision Materials

Inadequate supervision materials are a major hindrance to the effective supervision of higher institutions. Some personnel of regulating agencies or commissions goes for assignment of programme accreditation without having adequate writing materials, plain sheet, calculators and recording devices. Ogunode, & Adanna, (2022) and Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) stated that inadequate working materials are a big problem facing the supervision of universities in Nigeria. Many supervisors deployed to various universities for supervision are not been provided with adequate working materials to carry out their assigned roles. Many professors assembled for verification exercises in many universities, were not provided with the verification forms and other supervisory materials. The inadequacy of these materials is preventing the effective supervision of universities in Nigeria. Adewale (2017); Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) opined that many commissions and agencies of the Federal Government do not have adequate working facilities to execute their mandates. He concluded that the inability of the Federal Government to adequately fund these commissions and agencies is responsible for the shortage of working tools.

Ineffective Capacity Building

Poor capacity building problem is a major issue in many establishments of the government including the National Universities Commission. The budgetary allocation for training and retraining of staff yearly is not adequate to train staff that are due for training. Only a few staff in most agencies and commissions in Nigeria are on training yearly due to a shortage of funding. Poor capacity development is a major challenge in government institutions including the National Universities Commission.

Poor Release of Budget

Many public establishments in Nigeria are faced with the problems of non-releasement of budget on time. The inability of most government agencies and commission not to access their budgetary allocation on time have affected their performance. Most of such commission cannot implement their programme because of the poor release of funds. This problem also is affecting the National Universities Commission. **Executive Secretary of the National Universities Commission, (2019)** observed that the issue of not releasing budgets on time was worsened by the delay factors in releasing budgets while in most cases the budgets were not even released. For instance, Professor Rasheed told the joint Committee that the universities had only received 10 per cent of their entire

allocation for 2019, while NUC got 19 per cent so far. The lull in capital releases had stifled the capacities of the universities to generate useful research and commercialise same as electricity which was needed had continued to swallow a major part of the university's resources ((NUC, 2022).

Importance of Providing Adequate Funding for National Universities Commission

The availability of funds plays a significant role in determining the provision of quality education at all levels. The number of funds made available during budgeting will go a long way in improving the provision of quality of education. Adequate funding will be of importance in the provision of quality university education in one or more of the following ways:

Infrastructural Development

The availability of funds is very important in the actualization of the goals and programmes of the National Universities Commission. The provision of adequate funds for the commission will enable them to carry out its mandate. The adequate funding of the National Universities Commission will aid the development of infrastructure. More funding will help the National Universities Commission in providing more facilities such as more furnished offices, ICT facilities, libraries and instructional materials. Available facilities will also be provided based on modern development while obsolete facilities will be discarded. This means that the higher the level of funding, the more the infrastructures that will be provided for teaching and learning. When public institution grows, the institutions need to purchase assets, such as vehicles and machinery, to keep up with the increased demands and extension of services. Adequate funding will enable the institutions to acquire new offices and IT equipment so that the staff or employees will have all the tools they need for their jobs and to improve the internal infrastructure. The institutions also need new machinery for better and faster service delivery. Public institutions sometimes require funding for the expansion of services and product development and prototype collection. Some products require prototypes that involve a lot of funds to acquire them. Further service development may also require a lot of resources, and it might require a new set of teams, and for that purpose, the organization may have to arrange funds for the employment of new staff. Many institutions are going sophisticated in terms of ICT transformation. Public institutions need more funds to develop their website and have a functional web address to enable them to communicate nationally and internationally with other sister institutions across the globe. These development tend to consume a lot of the costs of the institutions as it requires a good team and platform as well as a good and efficient team. Also, public institutions like the National universities commission need additional funds to launch their services of effective supervision.

Employment of Quality Staff

Adequate funding from National Universities Commission will help the commission to employ more qualified staff. The availability of funds is very crucial in the employment of quality staffers. Adequate staff in National Universities Commission will enable the commission to discharge its mandate. With over two hundred universities across the country, there is a need to employ more staff. The increment in the budgetary allocation of the commission will help the commission expand its human resource. Various studies have shown that the higher the financial resources available to institutions, the more staff they employed. It is, therefore, necessary that funds should be provided to acquire this crucial human resource. This is because the presence of qualified personnel will help in discharging quality services. Public institutions like the National universities commission need adequate funding to enable them to employ new staff. Every year, old staff are retiring and need replacement. National universities commission need staff in different departments like accounting and finance, marketing, legal and consulting team, planning, accreditation, research and development etc. Considerable costs can be involved in the recruitment and selection process. Even after that, the orientation of such teams also entails a lot of costs such as training. Ade (2017) submitted that organizations with qualified and adequate human resources achieve their objectives

more than those without adequate staff. The payment of high wages and salaries is now used to attract quality personnel and this is based on the availability of funds.

Effective Capacity Building

The provision of adequate funds by the federal government to the National Universities Commission will help the commission train and retrain its staff. Training and retraining programme is key to the realization of organizational objectives. The National Universities Commission needs to train its personnel regularly to increase their capacity. With the high number of staff in the commission, the commission would need a huge sum of funds to provide quality training and retraining programme for its staffers. Training is very critical in supervisory institutions because their mandate involves capacity. Training and development help institutions gain and retain top talent, increase job satisfaction and morale, improve productivity and achieve the objectives (Ottawa (2021). Studies show that organizations engaged in employee development witness increased performance compared to organizations not committed to employee engagement. Dedicated training and development foster employee engagement, and a more efficient, competitive, and engaged workforce is critical to the organization's performance. Furthermore, 93% of employees will stay longer when a company invests in career development. Also, Regular training and development programmes can prevent workplace idleness and in turn will help organizations establish regular re-evaluation of their employee's skills and competencies. Furthermore, it will influence institution culture by instilling an emphasis on planning and can prompt organizations analysis and planning as it requires employers to review existing talent and evaluate growth and development opportunities internally, rather than via recruitment. Also providing opportunities for employees to explore new area, refine their skills, expand their knowledge and can help team members to bond with each other. During these training and development sessions, they will tackle new challenges together. They can also lean on one another for various learning opportunities by collaborating with colleagues who have specific areas of expertise. Research has shown that peer collaboration is a preferred method of learning. Learning from each other's strengths not only leads to a more well-rounded workforce, but those bonds can also improve retention and engagement (Ottawa (2021). Ogunode & Oluseun, (2020) and Ojo (2018) recommended that higher institutions and National Universities Commission should train their staff regularly to improve their skills and ability. Adequate funding of the National Universities Commission by the federal government is a very important step towards development of human resources in the commission.

Expansion of Zonal Offices in all the Geopolitical Zone

The increment in the budgetary allocation of the National Universities Commission will help the commission to expand its offices to each geo-political zone in the federation. There is a need for the National Universities Commission to establish more offices across the country to help the National Universities Commission achieve fast and reliable services to all the universities across the country. The limited offices of the commission are affecting the commission seriously. Ogunode & Adana (2022) observed that one of the major problems hindering the effective supervision of higher institutions in Nigeria is that the educational commissions such as the National Universities Commission [NUC], National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE] and the National Board for Technical Education [NBTE] operate from the head office only without having some offices at the geo-political level to attend to the issue of supervision of higher institutions located at the geo-political zones. The inability of these commissions to have offices in the geo-political zone hampers the effectiveness of their supervision. In this case, all issues must be handled by the head office. The provision of adequate funds to the commission will enable the commission to establish these offices and expand its services closer to the various universities across the country. The development of public institutions depends on the availability of funds. Musa (2017) opined that if an organization wants to expand and succeed in the long term, the institution will need enough

funds to implement the plans and goals of the organization. This growth can involve maybe employing new talent, expanding the services and programme the institutions are providing or moving into bigger and better head offices or headquarter. Having adequate funds helps the organization meets its need and implement its programme where necessary.

Effective Programme Accreditation

Adequate funding of National Universities Commission will help the commission carry out its cardinal goal of programme accreditation. Programme accreditation is one of the cardinal goals of the National Universities Commission in Nigeria. To carry out this responsibility annually request a huge sum of funds. The increment in the budgetary allocation to the commission can help the commission achieve more in the delivery of its mandate. Programme accreditation is an expensive exercise that needs a lot of funds (Ogunode, Ugochukwu, & Iroegbu, 2022 and Ogunode, & Ayoko, 2022). Any private or public organization needs adequate resources regardless of whether they are in its developmental phase or an expansion phase. To operate well, institutions have to incur certain fixed costs and certain variable costs in both the short, medium and long term. Under fixed costs, the institutions can expect expenses like machinery and equipment, while under variable costs, expenses include any raw materials that the company needs for its production process. **For example**, in the case of service production like supervision, the fixed cost would be the machines required for supervisory materials and computing machines and the vehicle for transportation, while the variable cost would include the paper, binding costs, etc. **Executive Secretary Prof. Abubakar Adamu Rasheed mni, (2019)** stated that the major component of NUC's capital was spent on hiring Professors in the universities for Accreditation of programmes and monitoring exercises in the Nigerian University System (NUC, 2019). Adequate funding will help the commission to meet up with the operating cost.

Quality Supervision

Quality supervision required a large sum of money. Supervision of educational institutions is highly financially demanding. A lot of human and material resources are requested to attain quality and effective supervision. Ogunode & Adana (2022) observed that supervision is key to the actualization of quality education at all levels of the educational system. Supervision is the process that involves providing a piece of professional advice and assistance to an individual or institution to improve the quality of the system. One major objective of supervision in an educational institution is to improve quality and ensure quality standards are maintained with the view of producing qualified products for the socio-economic and technological advancement of the country. The number of both private and public universities in Nigeria has increased to about 220 implying that more human and materials resources will be required. Sustainable funding of the National Universities Commission will guarantee effective university supervision in Nigeria. In defending the NUC's budget, Prof. Rasheed (2019) stated that "the roles and responsibilities of the Commission had continued to expand with the supervision of 172 universities made up of 45 Federal universities, (which include the two additional Federal Universities of Agriculture, Zuru, Niger State and Federal University of Medical Sciences, Otukpo, Benue State, though yet to fully become operational), 48 State and 79 Private universities. The commission also has about 104 affiliate institutions as members of the wider Nigerian University System (NUS), under its purview ((NUC, 2019). This makes the commission need adequate funding to be able to supervise all the institutions effectively".

Improve Quality of Service

The provision of adequate and sustainable funding of the National Universities Commission will help the commission to improve the quality of its services to universities across the country. When institutions in Nigeria are properly funded, there will be an improvement in the standard of services such institutions are providing and this will increase the level of patronage of the institutions. This in a long run can help to improve the image of the organization. Proper funding of National

Universities Commission will improve the internal efficiency and effectiveness of the institutions. To function properly public institutions and private organizations have adequate funds to enable them to carry out their constitutional responsibilities. Funds simply mean financial resources provided for an organization to work with. So, it is something that is needed for the proper functioning of the organization. This includes funds for recruitment of staff and purchasing of working facilities, etc. Not having enough working funds can impact severely the organization's programme and goals. Adequate funding of public institutions helps the institutions meet up with any unforeseen expenses and also covered other costs.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper examined the importance of providing adequate funding to the National Universities Commission for effective university supervision in Nigeria. The paper looked at the concept of the National Universities Commission, the functions of National Universities Commission, challenges facing National Universities Commission and the concept of university supervision. The paper in the area of challenges identified: inadequate funding, shortage of personnel, opposition from labour unions, inadequate supervision materials and ineffective capacity building as the challenges facing the National Universities Commission in Nigeria while in the area of adequate funding concluded that adequate funding of National Universities Commission will lead to; infrastructural development, employment of more staff, effective capacity building, expansion of zonal offices, effective programme accreditation, improve the quality of universities supervision and services. The paper finally recommended that;

1. The government should increase the funding of the National Universities Commission in Nigeria.
2. The government should block all financial leakages and corruption to allow for more funds in the hand of the government.
3. Public private partnership (3P) should be encouraged for effective collaborations and synergies

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